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The Relationship between Teachers' Motivation and Organizational Commitment: The Mediating Role of Perceived Principal Management Style

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Abstract

In this study, it is aimed to examine the mediating role of school principals' management styles in the relationship between teachers' motivation and organizational commitment. In the study, teachers working at all levels of education in public schools in the city center of Isparta in the 2021/2022 academic year constitute the universe. Simple random sampling method was preferred in the selection of the study group and data were collected from 962 teachers who volunteered. At the end of the extreme values, normality and multiple normality controls in the data set, 933 teachers were determined as the study group of the research. The perceived principal management style scale developed by Üstüner (2016), the organizational commitment scale for teachers developed by Üstüner (2009) and the adult motivation scale developed by Tulunay Ateş and İhtiyaroğlu (2019) were used as data collection tools in the research. The model established regarding the mediating role of management style in the relationship between teachers' motivation and organizational commitment was tested with the structural equation model. The demographic information, reliability coefficients and correlation values between the variables of the research participants were analyzed by SPSS 22, and the structural equation modeling was analyzed by LISREL 8.80. According to the research findings, relations between teachers' motivation, organizational commitment and perceived principal management style were determined. In addition, according to another finding of the research, the perceived principal management style has a partial mediating role in the relationship between teachers' motivation and organizational commitment. According to these findings, it can be interpreted that the effect of school principals' management style should be taken into account in increasing teachers' motivation and organizational commitment.

Keywords: Motivation, Organizational Commitment, Perceived Principal Management Style, Structural Equity Modeling, Mediation Role

1. Introduction

The Based on the information revealed by neoclassical theory; It can be said that the labor and productivity of the employees are affected by their emotions, thoughts and behaviors and related factors. Among these factors that

affect employees, there are also concepts such as commitment and motivation. As the motivation and organizational commitment of organization members and the relationship between them are important for the organization, they are the subjects that are included in many books written in the field of organization and management (Balay, 2014; Eren, 2012; Özkalp & Kırel, 2016 ve Sabuncuoğlu & Vergiliel Tüz, 2013) and researched (Cemaloğlu, 2002; Coladarci, 1995; Dogani, 2010; Hiriyappa, 2018; Karadaş, 2012; Karaköse & Kocabaş, 2006; Liou, 2008; Riehl & Sipple, 1996; Terzi & Kurt, 2005; Tulunay, Ateş & İhtiyaroğlu, 2019; Üstüner, 2016; Yazıcı, 2009; Yılmaz, 2009; Yıldız, 2013). Karadaş, Teke and Demir (2011) state that the motivation and organizational commitment of organization members in organizations should be increased for achieving the aims of the organization. With this perspective, It can be interpreted that the relationship between motivation and organizational commitment in organizations is very important. In other words, the behavior of the managers is effective in the job satisfaction of the organization members (Erdil et al., 2004) and the level of alienation from work (Şimşek et al., 2006). The fact that managerial behaviors can affect employees from different aspects suggests that they may also affect motivation and commitment.

The concept of commitment is expressed as individuals' feeling a high degree of responsibility towards something, an institution, an idea that they consider more important than themselves (Ergun, 1975). The concept of organizational commitment, which was first investigated by White in 1956, has been discussed by different researchers over time (Gül, 2002; Gül, 2014). Researchers who dealt with organizational commitment in the following years revealed in their studies that this concept is not a single dimension but also a concept that includes different dimensions. For example; Meyer and Allen define the concept of organizational commitment in the dimensions of affective, continuance and normative commitment; Mowday behavioral and attitudinal commitment dimensions; Etzioni moral, calculating and alienating dimensions of commitment; Kanter in the dimensions of continuance, unity and control commitment; Chatman and O'Really discussed internalization, adaptation and identification under the dimensions of commitment (Demirel, 2020). Porter et al. (1974) described by three factors organizational commitment as strong belief and acceptance of the organization's goals and values, the willingness to exert effort on behalf of the organization and a firm desire to continue membership in the organization.

Employees' commitment to the organization is important in all organizations, as well as a vital situation in schools located at the center of the education system (Karayılan, 2021). Since teachers are at the center of communication with both administrators and students in educational organizations, teachers' commitment to the school is of great importance (Celep, Bülbül & Tunç, 2000). Because, in order for teachers to work effectively and willingly, they are expected to develop a commitment to the school as well as their commitment to their profession and students. For this reason, it is necessary to eliminate all factors that negatively affect teachers' commitment levels (Yıldız, 2013). In this way, it is stated that the effectiveness of schools will increase thanks to teachers whose organizational commitment levels will increase (Elliot & Crosswell, 2003; Web, Metha & Jordan, 1992). Because it is stated that teachers with high organizational commitment are more effective in increasing student achievement due to being more interested in their students, while teachers with low organizational commitment have a negative impact on student success because they are less tolerant and less understanding towards their students (Balay, 2014; Riehl & Sipple, 1996) Considering that school success is measured by student success, it is stated that teachers with high organizational commitment will increase the success of the institution by raising more successful students (Karadaş, 2013) and will be ready to serve the school well (Bogler & Somech, 2004).

Dannetta (2002) states that teacher commitment has three dimensions.

- 1) Organizational commitment can be described as belief and acceptance of organizational goals and values, willingness to exert effort on behalf of the organization and the desire to stay in the organization (Mowday, Steers & Porter, 1982).
- 2) Commitment to the teaching profession; It is the degree to which a person has a positive, emotional commitment to his or her job (Coladarci, 1992).
- 3) Commitment to students' learning; It is about how committed teachers are to their students' learning, regardless of other issues that may be relevant (for example, academic difficulties, social background) (Kushman, 1992).

When the three dimensions mentioned above are carefully examined, it can be interpreted that organizational commitment is very important for teachers and that teachers with high organizational commitment will exhibit positive behaviors for the school, students and themselves.

There can be many factors that affect the motivation of individuals about a subject (Çetinkaya, 2018). For example, Ağca (2014) mentions that school administrators' management style and practices are highly effective in teachers' organizational commitment. Another factor that affects organizational commitment is motivation. Because it is stated that the organizational commitment of employees with low motivation is also low (Sarikaya, 2016). For this reason, it would be useful to examine the relationship between organizational commitment and motivation in detail.

Hiriyappa (2018) argues that the concept of motivation is difficult to understand and define. Therefore, it is natural to have different definitions of motivation. For example; This concept, which is reproduced from the word "movere", stands for activating in Latin, means activating individuals for organizational purposes within the organization (Tanrıöğen, 2018). In addition to, Kanfer (1990) describes motivation as the direction of person's effort level and a psychological process that enables one to cope with these obstacles in the face of obstacles. Therefore, it can be interpreted that the main source of initiating, directing and maintaining human behaviors is motivation (Çetinkaya, 2018). According to Keser (2006), motivation; It consists of three basic components: activating the impulses that exist in the nature of the individual and directing his behavior through environmental factors, evaluating the behavior in line with the goal to be achieved and maintaining the behavior in order to reach the goal by the individual.

Motivation can emerge as a result of internal and external sources (Robbins, 1999). Intrinsic motivation is based on an innate tendency to interact effectively with one's environment and make sense of one's own world (White, 1959). For this reason, in intrinsic motivation, the individual performs the behavior voluntarily for his own good, and the source of motivation is actually performing that job, that is, the behavior itself (Hackman & Oldham, 1976). Individuals who are motivated by external factors perform the behavior to obtain material or social awards or to refrain recompense. For this reason, the source of motivation is not the behavior itself, but the consequences of the behavior (Robbins, 1999).

The main reason why individuals who are both internally and externally motivated in organizations are motivated is the benefit they derive from organizations (Robbins, 1999). In return for the benefit it provides to the members of the organization, it obtains inputs such as time, effort, experience, knowledge and skills of the members of the organization (Jones, George & Hill, 1999). As a result of the mutual benefits among the organization and the member, the members of the organization are motivated internally in situations such as autonomy, responsibility, success and enjoyment of work while they are externally motivated in situations such as wages, job security, employee benefits and rest times (Robbins, 1999). Consequently, it is important to try to grasp what motivates individuals internally and externally (Dogani, 2010). For this reason, It can be said that motivating the members of the organization well and determining their motivation sources correctly are some of the most important duties of principals in organizations (Karaman, 2010).

Some peculiarities of the motivation process can be mentioned. For example; Yıldırım (2006) lists the characteristics specific to motivation as follows.

- What motivates people may differ from person to person.
- Whether the motivation process is successful or not can only be possible with good observation of human behavior.
- When a need is motivated and satisfied, new sources of motivation are needed.
- Although it is difficult for managers to control the motivation of individuals, it may be possible to influence the motivation process.
- People can be motivated without even realizing it.

Motivation is very important for productivity and success in schools, as in organizations outside the school (Herzberg, 2003). Because the teachers are at the center of this organization (Bursalioğlu, 1987) and because teachers have a significant role in the learning process as an example to students (Farid, 2011), the concept of

motivation can be expected to be even more important in schools. Although many teachers try to give their best for their students, there are many factors that prevent teachers from being motivated in the school environment (Darling-Hammond, 1999). On the other hand, organizational members who are motivated in the organization; It can be said that motivating teachers is important in terms of increasing teacher productivity since they will show responsible, organizational and self-directed behaviors (Vaughan, 2005).

Motivation is very important in terms of teachers' duties and responsibilities (Cemaloğlu, 2002). Similarly, Sarı, Arıganoğlu, and Cananoğulları (2018) state that teachers with high motivation will tend to take more responsibility. While a significant relation exists among teachers' motivations with their job satisfaction and work performance, highly motivated teachers also have a positive effect on student achievement (Yılmaz, 2009). Although teachers motivation is a combination of internal and external motivation levels at different rates, it is expected from teachers to fulfill their duties with internal motivation (Yazıcı, 2009). Because a high level of intrinsic motivation brings success (Lin, McKeachie & Kim, 2003). On the other hand, it is stated that teachers with low motivation levels may experience some negative situations and stress level is one of them (Pithers & Fogarty, 1995).

On the other hand, one of the important issues on motivation and organizational commitment is the management manner applied by the principals (Omidifar, 2013). Because the management attitude applied by the managers; It has an impact on teachers' motivation (Ada, et al., 2013) and organizational commitment (Ağca, 2014). Each manager may prefer a different management approach. In this case, the rate of motivating teachers may also change (Sarı, Arıganoğlu & Cananoğulları, 2018). The management styles adopted by the managers have been classified in different ways by some authors. For example; While Terzi and Kurt (2005) discuss the management styles of managers in three dimensions as "democratic", "authoritarian" and "indifferent"; In the "Perceived Manager Management Style Scale" improved by Üstüner (2016), four dimensions are considered as "cooperative-democratic", "authoritarian", "disinterested" and "oppositional" management styles. Since the "Perceived Manager Management Style Scale" improved by Üstüner (2016) was used in the current study, it was preferred to examine this classification.

Cooperative-democratic management approach

According to this management approach, the school administrator encourages teachers to work with the administrators while including them in the decision-making process by getting help from the teachers when necessary (Sarı, Arıganoğlu & Yalçın, 2014). In addition, administrators who adopt the cooperative-democratic management style try to develop cooperation between teachers, appreciate teachers and expect them to follow new developments (Üstüner, 2016).

Authoritarian management approach

In this management approach, administrators make teachers feel that there is a power difference between them and expect teachers to be aware of this (Sarı, Arıganoğlu & Yalçın, 2014). Üstüner (2016) states that administrators of this style are strict and intolerant, do not take teachers into account when participating in decision-making, and act too formally towards teachers.

Disinterested management approach.

School principals who adopt this management style do not give importance to the relationships between stakeholders at school, the feelings of the teachers, the problems of the school and the success of the school. They almost leave school alone (Sarı, Arıganoğlu & Yalçın, 2014). In addition, school principals who adopt this style also exhibit behaviors of constantly delaying the solutions of problems and being unfair among employees (Üstüner, 2016).

Resistive management approach

Managers in this style prefer to complicate problems instead of solving them, and they do not like breaking the rules and disrupting the routine (Üstüner, 2016). In addition, they do not support the work done by the teachers and try to prevent these studies (Sarı, Arıganoğlu & Yalçın, 2014).

Which attitude the administrators will choose depends on their personality traits (Ergin, 2008). In addition to the personality traits of the managers, the personnel profile they work with, the structure of the organization, the characteristics of the organization, the nature of the work done and the time constraints can also affect the management attitude that the managers will apply (Üstüner, 2016). Therefore, the attitude of the manager, which is affected by many factors and is clearly defined separately from each other as stated in the above headings, may sometimes change. With another expression, a manager can exhibit more than one and different attitudes together or separately, depending on the situation.

Although there are many studies that affect teacher motivation at school, the most important factor affecting teacher motivation is the attitude of the administrator (Eyal & Roth, 2011). In addition, Sun (2004) states that the management styles applied by the administrators are also effective in the organizational commitment of the teachers. It may be important to examine the relationships between these concepts because the management styles that principals applied have an impact on teachers' motivation and their organizational commitment. For this reason, it is intended to investigate whether the school principals' management style has a mediating role in the relationship between teachers' organizational commitment and motivation.

2. Methodology

This study is a descriptive study, one of the relational screening models, aiming to examine whether school principals' management style has a mediating role in the relationship between teachers' motivation and organizational commitment.

In this study, model 1 and model 2, in which the relationships between variables will be tested, are given in figure 1.

Figure 1: Research Models

As seen in Figure 1, while the relationship between teachers' motivation and teachers' organizational commitment was examined in Model 1, the mediating role of managerial attitude in the relationship among teachers' motivation and organizational commitment was investigated in Model 2.

2.1 The Study Group

The research group consists of teachers at all levels working in public schools in the center of Isparta in the 2021/2022 academic year. Data were collected from teachers who volunteered to participate in the study by using simple random sampling method in selecting the participants. In the first stage, data were collected from 962 teachers, but after the extreme data, normality and multiple normality checks the data that did not provide the normality and multiple normality assumptions were removed and 933 participants were determined as the final study group of the study. Demographic information of the study group is given in the findings section.

2.2 Data Collection Tools

2.2.1 Perceived Principal Management Style Scale

The scale, which aims to measure school principals' management styles according to teachers' perceptions, was improved by Üstüner (2016). The scale consists of 25 items in total, 7 items in the dimension of "cooperative" management style, 7 items in the dimension of "authoritarian" management style, 7 items in the dimension of "indifferent" management style, and 4 items in the dimension of "oppositional" management style. Scale items are graded as 5-point Likert-type (1) "never", (5) "always". In the 1st dimension, a maximum of 35, a minimum of 7 points, a maximum of 35, a minimum of 7 points in the 2nd dimension, a maximum of 35, a minimum of 7 points in the 3rd dimension, and a maximum of 20 and a minimum of 4 points in the 4th dimension can be obtained from the scale. The Cronbach's Alpha values related to the reliability of the scale are cooperative .92, authoritarian .89, irrelevant .86 and oppositional .85. In this study, Cronbach's Alpha values were found to be cooperative .96, authoritarian .87, irrelevant .78 and oppositional .84 in the reliability analyzes of the scale

2.2.2 Organizational Commitment Scale for Teachers

The single-factor and 17-item scale was developed by Üstüner (2009) to measure teachers' organizational commitment. The scale is in the form of a 5-point Likert scale and has a rating of (1) "never" and (5) "always". The Cronbach's Alpha internal reliability coefficient of the scale was determined as .96. In this study, Cronbach's Alpha value was found to be .97 in the reliability analysis of the scale.

2.2.3 Adult Motivation Scale

The scale improved by Tulunay Ateş and İhtiyaroğlu (2019) consists of 2 dimensions and a total of 21 items, 13 items in the "intrinsic motivation" dimension and 8 items in the "extrinsic motivation" dimension. The scale items are in a 5-point Likert type and are graded as (1) "strongly disagree" and (5) "strongly agree". The score that can be obtained from the scale is a minimum of 21 and a maximum of 105. The Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient for the reliability of the scale was calculated as 0.94. In this study, the Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient for "intrinsic motivation" was calculated as 0.89 and the reliability coefficient for "extrinsic motivation" was calculated as 0.72.

2.3 Data analysis

When analyzing data, some steps mentioned below were followed in order to determine whether the assumptions required for structural equation modeling were met. First, missing data was checked and three data were cleared from the data set. In addition, Mahalanobis distances of the data were calculated in order to calculate the multivariate extreme values. As a result, data that did not have multivariate outliers were excepted from the data set. At the end of the all these procedures, skewness and kurtosis values were examined with the data of the remaining 933 participants for testing the normal distribution. These values were found to be between -1.5 and +1.5. According to this, it can be said that the data exhibit a normal distribution (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013). SPSS 22.00 for descriptive statistical values and LISREL 8.80 for confirmatory factor analysis and structural equation modeling were used in the research.

3. Results

The demographic information of the teachers who constituted the study group of the research are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Information of Teachers

		f	%
Gender	Male	399	42,8
	Female	534	57,2
	Total	933	100
Teaching Level	Pre-School	72	7,7
	Primary School	217	23,3
	Secondary School	250	26,8
	High School	393	42,1
	Total	933	100
Operation Time	1-3 years	382	40,9
	4-6 years	224	24
	7-9 years	131	14
	10-13 years	102	10,9
	14 years and above	92	9,9
	Total	933	100
Seniority	1-10 years	206	22,3
	11-20 years	382	40,3
	21-30 years	276	29,8
	31-40 years	69	7,6
	Total	933	100

When Table 1 is examined, it is seen that 42.8% (n:399) of the teachers participating in the research are male and 57.2% (n:534) are female. In addition, 7.7% (n:72) of the participants are preschool teachers, 23.3% (n:217) are primary school teachers, 26.8% (n:250) are secondary school teachers and 42.1% (n:393) are high school teachers. In addition, when the working time of the participants at their school is examined, it is determined that 40.9% (n:382) is between 1-3 years, 24% (n:224) is between 4-6 years, 14% (n:131) is 7-9 years, 10.9% (n:102) is 10-13 years and 9.9% (n:92) is 14 years or more. Finally, It is seen that they have 22.3% (n:206) of the participants were between 1-10 years, 40.3% (n:382) between 11-20 years, 29.3% (n:276) between 21-30 years and 7.6% (n:69) between 31-40 years professional seniority.

Before the structural equation modeling analysis; In the scale of teachers' organizational commitment, consisting of a total of 17 items and one dimension, 2 parcels were created by using the item parceling method. It is aimed to benefit from the advantages (Süral-Özer, Eriş, & Timurcanday-Özmen, 2012) of using one-dimensional variables together with the item parceling method to provide more model fit to be an alternative to the weaknesses of factor analysis and to be used in organizational and psychological research. After the exploratory factor analysis, the items of the scale were according to their factor loads; Those with the lowest and highest factor loads were divided into two parcels. Thus, 2 latent variables, 1 observed in the organizational commitment scale for teachers, were obtained. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Analysis was carried out in order to reveal the relationships between teachers' organizational commitment, motivation and perceived principal attitude. The correlation, mean and standard deviation values between the variables are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Correlation, Mean and Standard Deviation Values between Variables

Variable	X	Sd	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
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1.C.M.S	4,07	0,98	1							
2.A.M.S	2,16	0,93	-.57**	1						
3.D.M.S	1,59	0,65	-.61**	.39**	1					
4.O.P.S	1,69	0,88	-.67**	.58**	.67**	1				
5. O.C.1	3,84	0,96	.78**	-.44**	-.53**	-.56**	1			
6. O.C.2	3,8	1,02	.81**	-.49**	-.54**	-.57**	.918**	1		
7. I.M.	4,62	0,36	.17**	-.10**	-.07**	-.06	.241**	.239**	1	
8. E.M.	4,24	0,47	.16**	-.05	-.05	-.02	.233**	.215**	.560**	1

*p<.05, **p<.01

C.M.S: Collaborative management style, **A.M.S:** Authoritarian management style, **D.M.S:** Disinterested management style, **O.P.S:** Opposing management style, **O.C.1:** Organizational commitment Plot 1, **O.C.2:** Organizational commitment 2. Plot, **I.M:** Intrinsic motivation, **E.M:** Extrinsic motivation

When Table 2 is examined, a highly positive and significant relationship ($r = .78$) was found between the 1st parcel of collaborative management hound and organizational commitment, A very high and positive correlation was found between the 2nd parcel of organizational commitment ($r = .81$) and a low level of positive correlation between intrinsic motivation ($r = .17$) and extrinsic motivation ($r = .16$). In addition, between the authoritarian management style and the 1st parcel of organizational commitment ($r = -.44$) moderately negative, between the 2nd parcel of organizational commitment ($r = -.49$) moderately negative and intrinsic motivation ($r = -.10$).) a low-level negative significant relationship was detected. Between the irrelevant management style and the 1st parcel of organizational commitment ($r = -.53$) moderately negative, between the 2nd parcel of organizational commitment ($r = -.54$) between moderately negative and intrinsic motivation ($r = -.07$) a low-level negative significant relationship was detected. Finally, a moderately negative significant relationship was found between the oppositional management style and the 1st parcel of organizational commitment ($r = -.56$), and a moderately negative significant relationship between the 2nd parcel of organizational commitment ($r = -.57$). The structural model of motivation and teachers' organizational commitment is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Structural Model of Teachers' Motivation and Organizational Commitment Variable

In Figure 2, it is seen that there is a coefficient ($\beta=0.38$, $p<.01$) showing the relationship between teachers' motivation and organizational commitment. Standardized coefficients are interpreted as low when they are less than 0.10, medium when they are around 0.30, and large when they are 0.50 and above (Kline, 2005: 122). Therefore, it can be said that motivation has a moderate effect on teachers' organizational commitment. When the fit indices of the model are examined ($X^2= 210.76$; $sd = 71$; $X^2 /sd =2.96$; $RMSEA = 0.00$, $RMR = 0.00$; $CFI = 0.98$; $GFI = 0.98$; $NFI=0.97$; $AGFI = 0.98$) values are generally good. . After this process, the model was tested by adding management style as a mediating variable to the model between motivation and organizational commitment. The t values of the obtained model are given in Figure 3, and the mediation role analysis including standardized values is given in Figure 4.

In Figure 3, principal management style t values are given in the relationship between teachers' motivation and organizational commitment.

Figure 3: Principal Management Style t-values in the Relationship Between Teachers' Motivation and Organizational Commitment

Jöreskog and Sörbom (1993) state that the critical t value should be above 1.96 for .05 significance level and above 2.576 for .01 significance level. In other words, it can be said that the relations below 1.96 for .05 significance level and 2.57 for .01 significance level are meaningless (Şimşek, 2020). When Figure 3 is examined, it has been determined that $t=4.90 > 2.57$ for teachers' motivation and principal management style, $t=6.46 > 2.57$ for teachers' motivation and organizational commitment, and $t=31.96 > 2.57$ for principals' management style and teachers' organizational commitment. From this point of view, it can be said that there are significant relationships between teachers' motivation, organizational commitment and principal management style.

In Figure 4, the mediating role of the principal's management style in the relationship between teachers' motivation and their organizational commitment and the relations between the variables are given.

Figure 4: The Mediating Role of Principal Management Style in the Relationship between Teachers' Motivation and Organizational Commitment

When Figure 4 is investigated, it is clear that there are positive relationships among the three variables. One-way arrows in the figure show one-way linear relationship. Each arrow means a hypothesis and a path that will correspond to the regression coefficient (Şimşek, 2007). In line with this information, according to the model obtained, it can be paraphrased that the effect of teachers' motivation on their organizational commitment occurs

both directly and indirectly through the principal's management style. In addition, as the model is investigated, it is determined that the collaborative management style is positive; it is also determined that there is a negative relationship between authoritarian, disinterested and oppositional management styles.

In addition, as the structural model in Figure 2 is investigated, it is seen that the effect of motivation on organizational commitment ($\beta=0.38$, $p<0.001$) decreased in the mediator model ($\beta=0.15$, $p<0.001$) in Figure 4. This decrease can be interpreted as evidence of the mediating effect of the manager's management style between motivation and organizational commitment and as a partial mediation. When the goodness-of-fit values of the last model tested in the study are examined ($X^2 = 284.14$; $sd = 74$; $X^2 /sd = 3.83$; $RMSEA = 0.07$; $RMR = 0.03$; $CFI = 0.96$; $GFI = 0.94$; $NFI = 0.96$; $AGFI = 0.87$) was found to be at a good level and sufficient (Cokluk, Şekercioğlu, & Büyüköztürk, 2012; Hu & Bentler, 1995; Kline, 2005).

4. Discussion

In this study, the mediating role of perceived principal management style in the relationship between teachers' motivation and their organizational commitment was examined. According to In accordance with the results of the correlation analysis and structural equation model made for this purpose; It has been determined that there is a moderate positive relationship between motivation and organizational commitment. As the literature is investigated, many studies examining the relationship between organizational commitment and motivation (Austen & Zacny, 2015; Bahrami et al., 2016; Canbaba, 2019; Ertürk, 2014; Fırat, 2012; Kalay, 2015; Mohan & Sharma, 2015; Oran, Bilir Güler) and Bilir, 2016; Özata and Topçu, 2018; Posey et al, 2015; Yılmaz, 2011; Yusein, 2013; Zeynel and Çarıkçı, 2015). On the other hand, many studies showing the significant and positive relationships between teachers' motivation and organizational commitment (Cansu, 2019; Ertürk; 2014; George & Sabapathy, 2014; Kalay, 2015; Oboko & Waswa, 2020; Tentama & Pranungsary, 2016; Uzunpınar, 2019) are available. As can be seen, the fact that the relationships between the organizational commitment and motivation of both employees and teachers are frequently studied by researchers can be explained by the importance of the relationship between motivation and organizational commitment. It is possible to confirm this important relationship with the finding of Johnson, Chang and Yang (2010) in their study that motivation is very important in increasing the organizational commitment of employees.

Another of the findings of this research is the relationship between teachers' motivation and perceived principal management style. There are some studies in the literature examining the relationships between teachers' motivations and perceived principal management style. For example, Abdurrezzak and Üstüner's (2020) finding that perceived management style is a significant predictor of teachers' intrinsic motivation is one of them. In addition, Sarı, Yıldız, and Canoğulları (2018) and Sun (2004) found significant relationships between perceived principal management style and teacher motivation, and Karataş (2020) found significant relationships between perceived principal management style and teachers' professional motivation. These relationships can be expected to vary according to perceived principal management styles. In the current study, it was determined that the internal and external motivations of the teachers had a positive effect on the collaborative management style, while it had a negative effect on the collaborative, authoritarian and oppositional management style. From this perspective, it can be interpreted that teachers who work with school principals who cooperate with teachers and adopt a management style that includes teachers in the decisions taken will be more motivated. On the other hand, considering that the collaborative management style has a positive effect on the school climate (Guzelgör, Demirtaş & Balı, 2021) and that the administrators with the collaborative management style also try to improve the cooperation between teachers and appreciate the teachers (Üstüner, 2016), It can be said that the collaborative management style will increase the working performance and their commitment to school of the teachers.

Finally, the mediating role of perceived principal management style in the relationship between motivation and organizational commitment was examined. When the fit indices of the obtained model were examined, it was seen that the values were generally high. According to the research findings, it is seen that teachers' motivations affect their organizational commitment both directly and indirectly through the perceived principal management style through partial mediation. This finding is a sign that the management styles of school principals' should be considered as an issue that should be considered in terms of teachers' motivation and organizational commitment.

Also the effect of the manager's management style should be taken into account in ensuring and increasing the organizational commitment of teachers.

Although this research is the first to investigate the impact of principals' management style on the relationship between teachers' motivation and organizational commitment in Turkey, it has some limitations. The research was executed only on teachers working in the city center of Isparta province. For this reason, it can be said that the generalizability is low. For this reason, more generalizable findings can be presented by conducting studies with larger samples in different provinces of Turkey.

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